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Visual Astronomy Display: November 2014

Katie Frey

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Visual Astronomy Display for November 2014

Highlights...

- MAVEN reached Mars in September and has begun **studying the upper atmosphere of the Red Planet** in an attempt to figure out what happened to the atmosphere of Mars;
- Unexpectedly, the Arctic and Antarctic regions react differently to changing climate conditions. A video from NASA Goddard discusses how, this year, **Antarctic sea ice reached a record maximum while the Arctic ice was at an minimum**;
- The spectra of light through a prism ranges from red to dark blue...so **where does the purple in a rainbow come from?** A video from MinutePhysics explores this question;
- On October 19, 2014, Comet Siding Spring made a close flyby of Mars, passing at a distance of only 87,000 miles! A video from JPL explains **how the Mars orbiters will evade destructive dust particles shed by the comet's near miss**;
- The NASA Langley Research Center explores the possibility of **floating a blimp through the atmosphere of Venus** in their video, HAVOC; and
- The European Space Agency teams up with Platige Image to create a **gorgeous short film called Ambition**, which showcases the Rosetta probe's mission to study comets as a source of water on Earth.

Flight over chaotic terrain

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Katie Frey leads the development of the Unified Astronomy Thesaurus, a community supported linked data vocabulary for sorting, filtering, and exploring astronomical literature, data sets, images, etc.

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